

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: APPIAH****FIRST NAME: MICHAEL****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student used Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirmed below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE RP1-RP5

1. What is an Academic Easy or Writing?

- An academic essay or scholarly writing is a nonfictional writing process produced as part of academic work and includes research findings or reports on empirical fieldwork.¹**
- Academic easy is any report by a researcher.
- It is a scholarly presentation by a researcher.
- It is a publication in a journal.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1 Fifth edition* (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2024), 7.

2. Why has American English gained prominence over British English?

- This is due to the population, wealth, the economy, the magnitude of higher education, and the appeal of American popular culture on language and habits.²**
- This is due to the political power of the US.
- The impact of the American culture on the world.
- Because the US is a superpower.

3. What is Research?

- Research is the systematic inquiry to answer a question the researcher and others want to solve.³**
- Research is the presentation of a report.
- It is an inquiry into a problem.
- It is to share your findings and conclusions with others.

² Ibid., 25-32

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, ninth edition*, revised. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colombo, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and the University of Chicago Press editorial staff (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 19.

4. What is a Research Argument?

- It is a conversation with a community of researchers or readers who are critical of your work.**⁴
- Stating your reasons and evidence.
- Finding a research question.
- An assertion that demands support.

5. What is Dissertation Research?

- Dissertation research is a gradual probe into significant research questions that contribute to the literature and demonstrate the skill of doctoral students to conduct research results.**⁵
- Dissertation Research is evidenced-based research questions.
- Dissertation Research is the final and actual completion of what was planned in the dissertation prospectus.
- It is evidence-based research.

6. What is schema?

⁴ Ibid., 56.

⁵ Edward Barroga and Glafera Janet Matanguihan, "A Practical Guide to Writing Quantitative and Qualitative Research Questions and Hypotheses in Scholarly Articles," *Journal of Korean Medical Science* 37, no. 16: e121, <https://doi.org/10.3346/jkms.2022.37.e121>. 2022.

- Schema is when one concept is broken into parts, and the idea of the research method is divided into parts, including research design, variables, measures, participants, data analysis, and delimitations.⁶**
- It is how researchers organize their dissertations.
- An abstract structure of information that researchers use.
- It is the recommended organization of Dissertation Components.

7. What is Jurisdiction-specific citation Rules?

- The referencing of local court rules and jurisdiction-specific manuals provides help on local court citation rules, which supersedes the Bluebook rules.⁷**
- Citations are used to cite authorities to help readers and researchers identify those authorities.
- They are Citation sentences and clauses found in Citations.
- Introductory signals include signals that indicate support.

8. What is the nature of Introductory Signals?

- Introductory signals are Signals that indicate support, Signals that suggest applicable compensation, Signals that indicate contradiction, and Signals as verbs.⁸**

⁶ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research Second Edition* (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 23.

⁷ Mary Prince Miles, *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation* (Cambridge, Mass: Harvard Law Review Association, 2013), 52.

⁸ Ibid.

- It is made up of substantial information in parenthetical order.
- It is a citation requiring multiple parentheticals to be placed in an order.
- It organizes authorities and how they relate to a proposition in the text.

9. Identify the elements of Cultural Diplomacy.

- Cultural Diploma is a diplomatic practice of governments carried out to support a government's foreign policy goals, which involves directly or indirectly the government's foreign ministry, which is involved in the exhibition of the state's culture, targeted at a broader population.⁹**
- It is how countries use cultural diplomacy to advance their interest in other countries.
- Using government ministries and departments, independent agencies, and non-profit organizations to advance foreign relations.
- Using literature, visual arts, theater, dance, and music to advance the interest of a country.

10. Identify the sources of law in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

- The principal sources of law are the Holy Quran and the Sunnah, as well as supplementary sources such as juristic preference and state regulations to deal**

⁹ Mark Simon, "A Comparative Study of the Cultural Diplomacy of Canada, New Zealand, and India" (PhD diss., University of Auckland, 2008), 8, <https://researchspace.auckland.ac.nz/docs/uo-docs/rights.htm>.

with modern legal problems arising from rapid development in diverse domains, customs, and practices.¹⁰

- The Regulation of Internal Commerce in 1938 was repealed by Law No.2 of 1960.
- The New York Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards 1958 by Law No.10 of 1978 (Abdullah 2010, 23).
- Sharia: according to the Kuwaiti constitution, ‘the Islamic sharia is the primary source of legislation and Constitutional law.

¹⁰ Alenezi Abdullah Mubarak Aldelmany, “An Analytical Study of Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards in the GCC States” (PhD diss., University of Stirling Scotland, 2010), 28.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Mubarak, Abdullah Aldelmany Alenezi. "An Analytical Study of Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards in the GCC States." PhD diss., University of Stirling, Scotland, 2010.
- Barroga, Edward and Glafera Janet Matanguihan. "A Practical Guide to Writing Quantitative and Qualitative Research Questions and Hypotheses in Scholarly Articles." *Journal of Korean Medical Science* 37, no. 16: e121. <https://doi.org/10.3346/jkms.2022.37.e121>. 2022.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 5th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024.
- Miles, Prince Mary. *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation*. 19th ed. Cambridge, Mass: Harvard Law Review Association, 2013.
- Sampson, James P. Jr. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. 2nd ed. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.
- Mark, Simon. "A Comparative Study of the Cultural Diplomacy of Canada, New Zealand and India." PhD diss., University of Auckland, 2008. <https://researchspace.auckland.ac.nz/docs/uoa-docs/rights.htm>.
- Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. 9th ed. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colombo, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and the University of Chicago Press editorial staff. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.